

The article is devoted to the problems of lingvocriminalistics as the section of science of the language. Meanwhile the main components and the practical use of the linguistic data in judicial expertise are considered. The idea of the importance of the linguistic knowledge for the workers of law enforcement agencies is emphasized. The article underlines the significance of phonoscopic expertise for law enforcement agencies.

Lingvocriminalistics, expertise, language, subculture, identification, insult, negative information, phonoscope.

Introduction.

In connection with Uzbekistan's desire for democracy and the rule of law, the role of new linguistic disciplines related to legal fundamentals is increasing. New disciplines have appeared (see, for example, "Introduction to linguistic forensics", "Linguistic aspects of criminal subculture", etc.), united by the general concept of linguistic forensics.

The term linguistic forensics has three meanings:

- 1) a branch of the science of language that studies text for legal purposes;
- 2) a section of linguistic science that teaches the preparation of forensic linguistic examinations;
- 3) a branch of the science of language that studies the sociolinguistic aspects of the criminal subculture.

Some scientists (for example, E. I. Galyashina, N. D. Golev) use the term jurislinguistics, understanding by it the first two meanings of the term linguistic forensics. However, in our opinion, the concept of linguistic forensics also includes an analysis of the elements of the subculture of the criminal world: slang, gibberish and conventional language, nicknames, tattoos, secret gestures and facial expressions, proverbs and sayings. There is an opinion that the main task of linguistic forensics is exclusively forensic linguistic examinations or identification of a person by his linguistic characteristics. But it would be a mistake to believe that the range of these examinations is limited to this. Almost all controversial issues related to language can be the subject of an expert linguist. Linguistic forensics as a branch of the science of language in a broad sense pursues the goal of studying text, in a narrow sense - compiling linguistic examinations, "... law also seeks answers to many questions in language" [4, p. 259].

Undoubtedly, training in conducting forensic linguistic examinations occupies a major part in the preparation of a forensic linguistic specialist. But, I think, practical law enforcement officials should also have a basic knowledge of linguistic forensics. Thus, researcher O. N. Kravchuk rightly believes that "a significant part of the materials sent for phonoscopic examinations to the EKV of the Central Internal Affairs Directorate of the Nizhny Novgorod Region are not suitable for identifying a person by voice and oral speech due to the low quality of the recording." She believes that this is to blame not only for the poor technical equipment of the police department, but also for the lack of preparedness of law enforcement officers [7, p. 16].

Main part. The most common forensic linguistic examinations are related to insult and negative information (protection of honor and dignity), establishing authorship, and the content of the concept of a trademark.

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Researcher E. I. Galyashina points to the practical use of linguistic data from law enforcement officers. "Special knowledge in linguistic disciplines," she emphasizes, "contributes to the extraction of various factual and personal data of negotiators and other forensically significant information from speech messages" [3, p. 17].

The expert linguist faces many unresolved questions. It will not be a revelation that the most important thing in court cases of insult is the list and nature of the offensive words. What lexemes are included in their composition, in which cases they can be offensive and in which they cannot, how slang-argotic words invective are treated from the point of view of certain social groups - these are the questions that a linguo-criminologist must answer. The books "The Price of the Word" and "Theory and Practice of Linguistic Analysis of Media Texts in Forensic Examinations and Information Disputes" have already made an attempt to classify offensive words, but it needs to be expanded and clarified. As the practice of working with law enforcement agencies shows, the latter are in dire need of methodological recommendations on the definition of verbal insult and the protection of honor and dignity. They need concrete examples. Some linguistic researchers propose compiling a dictionary, where "a new system of lexicographical marks should be developed (for example, offensive, indecent, negatively evaluative, etc.), reflecting the gradation of invectiveness" [9, p. 54]. Undoubtedly, such a dictionary can be compiled. But the question immediately arises about the implementation of these lexemes in the context and speech situation. The reasoning above does not mean that the authors of the article are against the creation of a dictionary of invective. On the contrary, this dictionary is necessary for both linguists and lawyers. The difficulty lies in giving a large number of examples for each invective, i.e., specific illustrations are needed, where in one case the word can be an insult, and where it can act in another function. However, this obstacle can be overcome: you need to use the most common speech situations.

Researcher V.I. Zhelvis focuses on the problem of "abusive weight of words," "since the concept of offensiveness is focused on the listener," that is, in social groups the same words can be perceived differently [5, p. 293]. Undoubtedly, in this case it is necessary to take into account both the subculture and the morality of certain societies. At the same time, we must be guided by the norms of literary language. For example, if a criminal called another criminal a trash heap or a mop, this would be an insult even in a law-abiding society. But in the criminal world, these words are very strong invective, that is, the speaker who utters them puts the opponent on the lowest rung of the criminal ladder, causing him a terrible insult.

Difficulty may arise in determining the nature of verbal abuse, which is associated with the perception and unintentional use of argotisms. For example, a law-abiding citizen called a professional criminal a dove (from blue - homosexual), an acrobat - a passive homosexual, paraffin - a person standing on the lowest rung of the criminal ladder, paraffin. In a criminal environment, these lexemes are considered obvious insults, but in a law-abiding environment, they will either be incomprehensible in a certain context or perceived as universal.

It seems that when writing a number of linguistic examinations, the historical aspect should be used. For example, expert researchers often ignore diachrony when analyzing offensive words, but it is known that even before the revolution, lawyers had the concept of offensive words, for example, professional invective, intellectual invective, sociomoral invective, pun invective, political invective, sacred. ineffectives.

During forensic linguistic examinations, questions arise related to clarifying the linguistic nature of a trademark. Sometimes it is necessary to resolve issues related to incorrect wording in legislation.

The main object of study of a linguo-criminologist is the text. It is usually understood as “a sequence of symbolic units united by a semantic connection, the main properties of which are coherence and integrity” [8, p. 507]. As can be seen from the definition, illustrations, various kinds of road signs, sailors’ symbols, etc. can be considered text. That is, any information that has a system. Any text (and therefore any information) appears and exists in a certain socio-cultural space. It is this that generates information and determines the mechanisms for its interpretation. Note that the time parameter is key for them.

Forensic phonoscopic examination is very important. This is a type of forensic speech examination aimed at establishing the identity of the speaker based on the characteristics of the voice and speech recorded on the phonogram, identifying signs of erasure, copying, editing and other changes introduced into the phonogram during or after the end of the sound recording, determining conditions, circumstances, means and materials sound recordings, as well as other facts relevant to forensic evidence [see: 3].

The specificity of forensic phonoscopic examination is that in order to solve many issues, the expert must have a wide range of knowledge from different fields of science and technology (linguistics and acoustics, mathematics, radio engineering, etc.). The objects of phonoscopic examination are sound, especially speech, information recorded on various media, sound recording media (tape recorders, video recorders, voice recorders, magnetic, optical and other media, etc.).

Recently, various technical systems for determining the speaker’s individuality based on speech characteristics have been actively developing. Interest in solving applied problems in this direction is determined by the presence of a wide range of practical applications, which can be divided into two broad classes: checking access rights to various systems (information and physical): communication channels, computer systems, databases, bank accounts, official and individual premises for limited use (secrecy, material assets, etc.), various devices and mechanisms (vehicles, weapons, etc.), etc.

Currently, when performing phonoscopic examination based on methods of linguistic analysis, the expert establishes the literal content of the statement, determines the number of speakers, identifies them based on the presented comparative samples of voice and speech, and resolves other issues.

solves other questions. In order to obtain high-quality experimental samples, the individual linguistic and phonetic characteristics of the speaker are identified on the phonogram of the person being identified. At the same time, materials submitted for comparative research should contain, first of all, words and phrases in which the peculiarities of pronunciation, speech pathology or other deviations from generally accepted norms of the literary language are most clearly manifested.

When studying a phonogram for editing, along with visual analysis of a magnetic medium using the magneto-optical method and instrumental study, today it is mandatory to involve a highly professional expert with a basic linguistic education to analyze the integrity, coherence, continuity and naturalness of recorded speech.

A typical task of linguistic research when identifying a speaker from speech recorded on a phonogram is to identify an intellectual functional-dynamic speech complex, i.e., an individual’s

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stable skills and abilities when generating statements in oral form. On this basis, not only identification, but also diagnostic problems related to establishing data about the speaker's identity from his voice and speech are solved [3, p. 124].

In some cases, it is necessary to determine from speech not the individuality of the speaker, but some group characteristic: age, the presence of a particular accent or regional type of pronunciation, the presence of voice pathology, etc. This type of task arises mainly in forensic examination or monitoring of communication channels. Most often, the solution to such problems is based on an auditory expert assessment of the analyzed speech message and uses automatic analysis methods only at the preliminary stage or as auxiliary ones.

One of the tasks of linguistic forensics is: familiarizing employees of the judicial and legal system with methods and techniques for interpreting texts, their interpretation, explaining the use of a linguistic sign, establishing the authorship of a text, identifying plagiarism, etc. A lawyer must have an understanding of the basic linguistic processes that can be discussed in forensic examinations: tautology, pleonasm, metaphor, metonymy, lexical meaning, euphemism, types of speech errors, etc. He must have a good knowledge of those linguistic terms that directly relate to forensic linguistic examination and the court: indecent form, negative information, obscene vocabulary, invective vocabulary, etc.

Conclusions.

Currently, comprehensive examinations are becoming effective, in which specialists from different fields of knowledge take part. A special role in them should be given to the expert linguist. Thus, when commissioning a complex forensic economic examination, you cannot do without special language knowledge that will help establish the identity of the person who wrote the documents, identify the text, etc. Meanwhile, linguistic issues are almost not considered in forensic economic examinations [see, for example: 2, p. 46] and the possible help of linguists still remains unclaimed. Sometimes complex examinations, in which a linguo-criminalist must participate, are called "non-traditional forensic psychological" [1, p. 51].

Criminologists usually divide all forensic examinations into twelve classes:

- 1) forensic;
- 2) medical and psychophysiological;
- 3) engineering and technical;
- 4) engineering and transport;
- 5) engineering and technology;
- 6) economic;
- 7) biological;
- 8) soil science;
- 9) agricultural;
- 10) food products;
- 11) environmental;
- 12) art history.

As you can see, linguistic expertise in forensic science is not identified as a special branch. It is included in the first class of examinations - forensic, which includes three types: A - traditional forensics, the formation of which relates mainly to the period of the emergence and development of forensic examinations; B – examinations that were formed in the last decades of the twentieth century; B – various types of research on materials, substances, products, classified as a separate

class, also called materials science. Expertise group A includes: auto-editing; ballistic; handwriting, portrait, technical forensic examination of documents; traceological; edged weapons [see. 6, p. 54–59]. As you can see, there is not even a mention of linguistic expertise in the description. Lawyers consider author's examination only as one of the categories of forensic examination. This “inequality” must change, since at present linguistic issues requiring resolution in jurisprudence are becoming more and more relevant. It is possible that linguistic expertise will be able to become an independent branch, since its concept includes all expertise related to the text. At the same time, it should combine all examinations related to language in one way or another: authorship, handwriting, documentation, examinations related to the concept of honor and dignity, insult, etc.

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